

Nutrient management in closed-loop soilless crop systems using ion selective electrodes and DSS NUTRISENSE

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Abstract

Dealing with the unknown mineral composition of the recycled drainage solution (DS) is a major challenge in closed-loop soilless crop systems (CLS). Currently, this issue is tackled through periodic laboratory analysis of DS followed by readjustment of the nutrient solution (NS). An attractive alternative approach involves using ion selective electrodes (ISEs) for direct measurement of macronutrient levels in the DS. However, to properly utilise the measurements obtained from the ISEs, suitable models based on mass balance and applied through an online operating decision support system (DSS) are needed. NUTRISENSE is a DSS operating online, which was designed specifically for managing nutrition in soilless crop systems. The main function of NUTRISENSE is the readjustment of the supplied nutrient solution (NS) based on the composition of the DS. If an ISE system is used, NUTRISENSE can recalculate daily the composition of the supplied NS based on the data obtained from ISEs to improve the accuracy of nutrient management. Furthermore, NUTRISENSE automatically transmits the corresponding fertiliser injection rates to a fertigation system that utilizes individual fertiliser stock solutions to implement in real time the new NS composition. To evaluate the nutrient management efficiency of NUTRISENSE when connected online with ISE, an experiment was conducted with cucumber plants grown in two CLS. The LAQUAtwin sensors (Horiba, Kyoto, Japan) were employed to measure the NO_3^- , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and Na^+ concentrations. In the control CLS, a standard NS composition was supplied, with EC and pH maintained close to the target levels. In the second CLS (ISE treatment), EC, pH, NO_3^- , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and Na^+ levels were daily measured using ISEs, while Mg^{2+} levels were calculated from EC values and the other cation concentrations based on the anion to cation balance principle. The data obtained from these measurements were subsequently introduced into NUTRISENSE to calculate the readjusted NS compositions and injection rates for each fertiliser. The LAQUAtwin ISEs proved to be highly accurate and the EC, pH, NO_3^- , K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} values measured in the DS were maintained close to the corresponding target values. The results showed that the algorithm deployed by NUTRISENSE to daily readjust the composition of the supplied NS using data from ISE measurements, is efficient and scalable for commercial application.

Keywords: Cucumber, fertigation, hydroponics, nutrient recirculation, nutrient management

INTRODUCTION

Soilless culture has become the primary cultivation method in modern greenhouse production. Closed-loop soilless culture systems (CLS) recycle fertigation effluents, *i.e.* drainage solution (DS), reducing surface and underground water pollution. The adoption of CLS can reduce water and fertilizer consumption by 30% and 40%, respectively, enhancing the sustainability of the greenhouse production (Grewal et al., 2010; Massa et al., 2011; Savvas and Gruda, 2018). This aligns with the EU Green Deal target of 50% nutrient loss reduction and 20% fertiliser consumption reduction by 2030 (European Green Deal, 2019). The pollution of surface and underground water caused by leaching and run-off of nitrates and phosphorous in greenhouse crops can be significantly reduced or even eliminated through the adoption of CLS.

The management of plant nutrition in CLS is challenging due to variations in DS composition over time. Savvas et al. (2024) reviewed current practises in CLS management and clarified the terminology. Regular DS analysis is critical to ensure optimal composition of the nutrient solution supplied to the plants (SS). Nutrient uptake varies throughout the plant life cycle, and therefore the nutrient supply has to be regularly readjusted based on the DS composition. Commercial greenhouses typically conduct laboratory analysis of the DS every 7-15 days, but real-time nutrient monitoring would optimise plant growth conditions. Ion selective electrodes (ISEs) constitute a promising technology for monitoring of the DS composition, but their commercial adoption is still very limited, as there are still no suitable DSS to utilise the obtained measurements (Chowdhury et al., 2020; Kim et al., 2017; Peña-Fleitas et al., 2021). NUTRISENSE is an online Decision Support System (DSS) designed to manage nutrition in soilless culture systems. The main function of NUTRISENSE is to regularly readjust the nutrient supply to the crop requirements during the growing season based on the DS composition (Savvas et al., 2023). The aim of this study is to exploit data of rapid measurements of DS composition using a suitable software. This strategy will increase the precision of nutrient management in CLS contributing in the adoption of an ecofriendly cultivation technique.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Outline of ISE - NUTRISENSE concept

In the current study, a new strategy for nutrition management of crops grown in CLS was tested. This strategy is based on daily determination of key macronutrient concentrations in the DS using ion selective electrodes (ISEs), and the DSS NUTRISENSE to automatically control the fertiliser injection rates based on the measurements of the ISEs. According to this strategy, the supply of the nutrients determined in the DS using ISEs is readjusted aiming to maintain their concentrations in the root solution (RS) up to the target levels suggested in the literature (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009). The algorithm is based on a mass-balance equation for each nutrient, which aims to accurately calculate the addition of stock solution fertilisers in the system, considering the natural and chemical restrictions, and the available equipment in the greenhouse unit. The composition of the RS is considered similar with that of the DS (Voogt and Bar-Yosef, 2019) and, therefore, henceforth they are both referenced as RS/DS. Furthermore, the ratios between the net nutrient and water supply to the plants (mmol L^{-1}) are considered concentrations of a nutrient solution termed added solution (AS), as suggested by Blok et al. (2023) and Savvas et al. (2024).

To readjust the nutrient supply, the algorithm recalculates the concentration of each nutrient in the supplied solution (SS) aiming to restore the target concentration of this nutrient in the RS/DS. The daily readjustment of the SS composition is possible using fertigation systems with single fertiliser stock solutions which allow for preparing nutrient solutions differing in their

composition merely by altering the injection rates of the stock solutions and the target EC. The most common fertigation systems of this type utilize eight tanks for the fertilisers and one for the acid used for pH adjustment. The fertilisers used for SS preparation are calcium nitrate, potassium nitrate, ammonium nitrate, magnesium nitrate, magnesium sulphate, potassium sulphate, monopotassium phosphate, iron chelate and nitric acid. The micronutrients Mn, Zn, Cu, B and Mo are added at a standard ratio in the stock solution of monopotassium phosphate and thus their supply rates are not altered when readjusting the concentrations of major nutrients in relation to the ISEs measurements. The limitations in NS composition arising from the available fertilisers and nutrients within each single fertiliser are also taken into consideration when readjusting the AS.

Experimental design

To evaluate the efficiency of the new strategy for nutrient management in CLS and the accuracy of the commercially available ISEs, an experiment with cucumber was conducted. The crop was established on the 22nd of June 2023 in a greenhouse of the Laboratory of Vegetable Production at the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA: 37°58'54.2"N 23°42'22.0"E altitude 35 m), while the supply and recycling of the DS started on the 27th of June 2023. The experiment was finished on the 8th of August 2023. Sixteen experimental plots were used, corresponding to sixteen gutters 6 m in length, with 6 stonewool slabs in each gutter, which were randomly allocated into two different treatments. In the first treatment, which served as control, an AS with a standard composition for closed soilless systems according to the recommendations of Sonneveld and Voogt (2009) was mixed with the recycled DS to prepare the outgoing SS, aiming at the standard EC suggested for open soilless cropping systems. In the second treatment (ISE treatment) the new strategy was applied which involved daily readjustment of the nutrient injection rates to the mix of DS and water based on ISEs measurements, aiming to prepare a readjusted SS with a composition that could restore the target macronutrient concentrations in the DS/RS, whenever they deviated from the target levels. More specifically, the concentrations of the macronutrients in the readjusted SS were those suggested in standard literature sources (de Kreij et al., 1999; Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009), plus/minus the amounts needed to restore the target concentrations in the RS/DS. The preparation and supply of the SS was performed using a fertigation system capable of injecting single fertiliser stock solutions (8+1 for the acid) in both treatments. The fertigation system was online connected with the DSS NUTRISENSE and thus, the readjusted injection rates of the single-fertiliser stock solutions and EC were automatically transmitted to the fertigation system. Then, the fertigation system was applying the injection rates and EC received from NUTRISENSE, up to their next readjustment on the next day.

Plant material, growth conditions and mineral analysis

Cucumber seedlings (*Cucumis sativus* L. cv. KLIMA RZ F1) were obtained by sowing seeds in stonewool cubes (7.5×6×7.5 cm). Eight 6-m long gutters were used with 6 slabs each were used as replications in each treatment. In each gutter, 12 cucumber plants were transplanted, resulting in a plant density of 2.4 plants m⁻². The plants were trained to single stem in a high wire system by removing all lateral shoots and 13 to 15 leaves were maintained per plant by weekly removing the lowest (oldest) leaves on the stem. The irrigation frequency was adjusted automatically in response to the solar radiation recorded by a pyranometer, aiming at a 0.3 drainage fraction. The temperature in the greenhouse maintained between of 28 to 35°C, and the relative humidity between 65-85%. The mineral composition of the raw water used to prepare NS was: EC: 0.3 dS m⁻¹, pH: 7.8, Ca²⁺: 0.9 mM, Mg²⁺: 0.3 mM, Na⁺: 0.5mM, SO₄²⁻: 0.2mM, Cl⁻: 0.3mM and HCO₃⁻: 2.2 mM.

On daily basis, a DS sample was collected from the ISE treatment at the same time, and the concentrations of K⁺, Ca²⁺, NO₃⁻ and Na⁺ were measured using the LAQUAtwin sensors (Horiba, Kyoto, Japan). Furthermore, the EC and pH in the DS sample were measured using HI98312 and HI8424 (Hanna Instr. Inc., Woonsocket RI, USA). The concentrations that were used as calibration points for each ISE are shown in Table 1. The Mg²⁺ concentration was calculated from the measured EC value and the measured concentrations of the other macrocations using the equation suggested by Savvas and Adamidis (1999, 2000):

$$\Sigma C^+ = 9.819E - 1.462$$

The obtained data was introduced to DSS NUTRISENSE. Using this data, NUTRISENSE calculated the injection rates of the single-fertiliser stock solutions needed to prepare SS with the readjusted composition and automatically transmitted these to the fertigation system. Upon receipt, the fertigation system automatically applied the readjusted fertiliser injection rates to prepare SS with the readjusted composition.

The macronutrient concentrations in the DS samples were additionally measured using standard analytical procedures and the obtained values were compared with those measured by the LAQUAtwin sensors to assess the reliability of the measurements obtained from the ISEs. The concentrations of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ were determined using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AA-7000, Shimadzu Corporation, Japan) while K⁺ and Na⁺ were measured by flame photometry (Sherwood Model 410, Cambridge, UK). NO₃⁻ was determined photometrically using a microplate spectrophotometer (Anthos Zenyth 200; Biochrom, MA, USA) by applying the vanadium chloride method at 540 nm (Schnetger and Lehnert, 2014).

Table 1. Concentrations used for the calibration of K⁺, Ca²⁺, NO₃⁻ and Na⁺ ISE (LAQUAtwin, Horiba, Kyoto, Japan).

Nutrient	K ⁺	Ca ²⁺	Na ⁺	NO ₃ ⁻
Low calibration point	3.84 mM (150 mg L ⁻¹)	3.74 mM (150 mg L ⁻¹)	0.65 mM (15 mg L ⁻¹)	2.42 mM (150 mg L ⁻¹)
High calibration point	15.35 mM (600 mg L ⁻¹)	14.97 mM (600 mg L ⁻¹)	6.52 mM (150 mg L ⁻¹)	32.26 mM (2000 mg L ⁻¹)

Statistical analyses

Statistical analysis was performed using the STATISTICA 12.5 for Windows (StatSoft Inc., Tulsa, USA). The graphical representation of the data was carried out using the GraphPad Prism 8 software (GraphPad Software, USA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.1 shows the evolution of the macronutrient concentrations in the DS collected in both the control and the ISE treatment during fifteen cropping days (from the 17th to the 31st of July) with daily readjustment of the SS composition in the ISE treatment. Whenever the concentrations of K, Ca, and NO₃⁻ in the ISE treatment tended to deviate from the target, they converged back to the target level on the next day. Overall, the concentrations of all macronutrients were more closely to the target in the ISE than in the control treatment. The measured values of the four

macroelements using ISEs were very similar with those obtained by involving standard analytical methods in the laboratory, indicating their suitability for commercial use in CLS.

Figure 1. Evolution of DS composition in the two treatments during fifteen days of implementation of the new strategy and corresponding measurements of ISE. The horizontal dotted line indicates the target level in DS for EC and nutrient concentrations.

The Mg concentrations calculated based on the empirical equation suggested by Savvas and Adamidis (1999, 2000), the EC and the K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Na⁺ concentrations, were accurate. The estimation results underline the accuracy of the ISE sensors for the other three cations and the suitability of the empirical equation for DS samples. In this framework, it is possible to readjust the supply of the three macronutrient cations (K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺) and nitrogen utilizing the measurements of EC, K⁺, Ca²⁺, NO₃⁻ and Na⁺ concentrations by credible ISE systems, such as the LAQUAtwin sensors. The correction of the Mg concentration exhibited a delay in the ISE treatment because Mg was removed from the system only due to plant uptake which is relatively low for this macronutrient, while its input could not be lower than its concentration in the raw

water. Nevertheless, the Mg concentration finally converged to the target level. The EC was maintained close to the target level in both treatments.

The ISE data were accurate and thus the algorithm operating through the DSS NUTRISSENSE achieved precise nutrient management, as the concentrations of all three measured macronutrients (K, Ca, NO₃⁻) and Mg tended to converge to the target level after each readjustment of the AS. The mass balance models and the algorithms used through the DSS NUTRISSENSE to optimise nutrient management in CLS have been already validated in previous experiments (Giannothanasis et al., 2023; Savvas et al., 2023), suggesting their efficiency. Hence, the results of the current study indicate that the measurements of individual macronutrient concentrations using suitable ion specific sensors operating off-line and supported through specialised DSS such as NUTRISSENSE can be used to effectively maintain the target nutrient concentrations in the RS/DS of soilless crops.

Figure 2. Linear regression between the results obtained using the ISEs analysis and the results obtained by standard laboratory analysis.

Fig. 2 shows the linear regressions between the ISE measurements and the corresponding measurements through standard laboratory procedures. The slope and intercept value for K were 0.9945 and 0.049 and the R² value 0.925. According to Cabrera Corral et al. (2016) and Stevens et al. (2016), K sensor measurements showed also linear relationships (R² values of 0.86 and 0.88, respectively) in soil extracts. The measured Ca and Na values also exhibited linear relationships between the two methods (R² values 0.946, 0.950, respectively) and slopes of 1.044

and 1.064 and intercept value of 0.086 and 0.124, very close to the 1:1 line. Cabrera Corral et al. (2016), found slope and intercept values for K, Ca, and Na, at 1.01, 1.087, 0.943 and 0.27, -1.75, 1.38, respectively, in soil solution samples. NO₃⁻ measurements exhibited also a linear trend (R² value 0.930) with a slope very close to 1 (1.006) and an intercept value of -0.364. Peña-Fleitas et al. (2021) also found a linear relationship between the ISE measurements and those obtained through standard analytical protocols (R² value 0.962) with a slope of 0.982 and intercept value of 0.755 in NS samples. All these results are consistent to the results of this study indicating the accuracy of K, Ca, Na and NO₃⁻ measurements with the LAQUAtwin sensors (Horiba, Kyoto, Japan) for rapid determination of macronutrient concentrations in DS samples.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the study demonstrates the efficacy of the proposed novel strategy for precise nutrient management in CLS using ISEs in conjunction with the DSS NUTRISense. By daily monitoring and readjusting nutrient levels based on ISE measurements, the strategy effectively maintained the macronutrient concentrations in the RS close to the target levels. The results indicate that the ISE measurements of the K⁺, Ca²⁺, NO₃⁻, and Na⁺ concentrations showed high accuracy compared to standard laboratory methods. Linear regressions between ISE measurements and standard protocols revealed strong correlations, confirming the reliability of the ISEs for rapid determination of macronutrient concentrations in DS samples. These findings underline the potential of the proposed approach to enhance nutrient management in CLS, contributing to sustainable greenhouse production by optimizing resource utilization and minimizing environmental impact. Further validation and implementation of this strategy could help for widespread adoption, aligning with the goals of promoting nutrient efficiency and reducing nutrient loss.

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